

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		N	M ^a	X ^b
Pt(dpa)I ₂	Yellow	6.52 (6.77)	31.97 (31.45)	40.73 (40.96)
Pd(dpa)I ₂	Yellow	7.74 (7.90)	19.52 (19.96)	47.57 (47.83)
Pt(dpa)Br ₂	Yellow orange	8.02 (7.98)	37.12 (37.02)	30.17 (30.41)
Pd(dpa)Br ₂	Yellow	7.53 (7.61)	24.18 (24.25)	35.45 (36.61)
Pt(dpa)Cl ₂	Light yellow	9.60 (9.61)	44.48 (44.62)	15.94 (16.26)
Pd(dpa)Cl ₂	Bright yellow	12.28 (12.06)	30.50 (30.45)	20.28 (20.40)
Pt(dpa)OX	Yellow	9.43 (9.24)	42.87 (42.95)	—
Pd(dpa)OX	Yellow	11.56 (11.50)	29.23 (29.04)	—
Pt(dpk)I ₂	Orange yellow	4.18 (4.42)	30.71 (30.80)	39.98 (40.12)
Pd(dpk)I ₂	Yellow	5.27 (5.14)	19.33 (19.48)	46.54 (46.69)
Pt(dpk)Br ₂	Yellow brown	4.98 (5.19)	86.25 (86.17)	29.36 (29.69)
Pd(dpk)Br ₂	Yellow	6.37 (6.22)	23.36 (23.55)	35.46 (35.55)
Pt(dpk)Cl ₂	Yellow	6.10 (6.22)	43.18 (43.33)	15.52 (15.77)
Pd(dpk)Cl ₂	Yellow orange	7.50 (7.75)	29.29 (29.36)	19.51 (19.66)
Pt(dpk)OX	Yellow	5.59 (5.99)	41.80 (41.75)	—
Pd(dpk)OX	Yellow	7.28 (7.40)	28.10 (28.04)	—

^aM = Pt or Pd. ^bX = Cl, Br or I.

~ 1580 cm⁻¹ in free ligands (dpa/dpk) shows a slight positive shift in all the complexes suggesting the chelation of the ligands to the metal via pyridine ring nitrogen atoms^{10,11}. This is further supported by the positive shifts of other ring breathing modes in the complexes as compared to those in the free ligands. The ν_{NH} and δ_{NH} vibration of dpa at 3300 and 1603 cm⁻¹ respectively and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ vibration of dpk at 1680 cm⁻¹, are not appreciably affected in the platinum and palladium complexes. This clearly indicate that NH of dpa and CO of dpk are not involved in metal binding. The analogous chloro complexes of Pt^{II} show two medium-intense to intense absorption bands at about 345 and 330 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{\text{Pt-Cl}}$ asymmetric and symmetric vibrations respectively, corresponding to two chloro groups in the *cis*-position^{12,13}. In case of the Pd^{II} complexes $\nu_{\text{Pd-Cl}}$ vibrations appear at about 325 and 310 cm⁻¹ respectively. The $\nu_{\text{M-Br}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-I}}$ vibrations appear at ~ 250 and ~ 200 cm⁻¹ respectively and hence have not been assigned. The presence of bands at ~ 1700, ~ 1650, ~ 1400, ~ 920 and ~ 820 cm⁻¹ in oxalato complexes suggests the bidentate oxalate ion coordination to platinum and palladium¹⁴.

The ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) were recorded using TMS as internal standard. The polypyridyl ligand proton signals were assigned following the ¹H nmr assignments of α - α' -diimine ligands^{15,16}. The H-6,6' proton signal of 2,2'-dipyridylamine

appearing as a doublet at δ 8.24, shifted to δ 8.24–9.14 in the platinum complexes and to δ 8.7–9.00 in the palladium complexes; while in case of 2,2'-dipyridylketone, the H-6,6' proton signal appearing at δ 8.74 as a doublet, shifted to δ 9.19–9.46 and 9.05–9.31 in the platinum and palladium complexes respectively. The shifts follow a trend, δ -chloro < δ -bromo < δ -iodo. The large downfield shifts of H-6,6' protons together with downfield shifts of other ligand protons, clearly indicate ligand binding to metal via pyridine rings. This is further confirmed by large values of ²J_{Pt-H} coupling constants (44–50 Hz) for ¹⁹⁵Pt–N–C–H fragments for the platinum complexes.

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Studies on Quaternary Complexes of some Lanthanones

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It is interesting to note¹⁻⁵ that in the formation of mixed ligand species, the trivalent lanthanides have a tendency to attain their unusual coordination number forming more stable complexes. This

Fig. 1. System 1:1:1:1, La^{III}-EDTA-CCA-MIA: (a) La^{III}-nitrate, (b) K₂EDTA, (c) CCA, (d) MIA, (e) La-EDTA, (f) La-CCA, (g) La-MIA, (h) La-EDTA-CCA, (i) La-EDTA-MIA, (j) La-EDTA-CCA-MIA, (T) theoretical composite curve and (→) appearance of ppt.

Fig. 2. System 1:1:1:1, La^{III}-IMDA-ODA-TRA: (b) IMDA, (c) ODA, (d) TRA, (e) La-IMDA, (f) La-ODA, (g) La-TRA, (h) La-IMDA-ODA, (i) La-IMDA-TRA, (j) La-ODA-TRA, (k) La-IMDA-ODA-TRA, (T) theoretical composite curve and (→) appearance of ppt.

led us to investigate some quaternary complexes of lanthanones by potentiometric method. Relative stability of the mixed species has been explained on the basis of increase in the number of fused rings, basicity of the ligands and ionisation potential of the metal ions.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

Standard solutions of rare earth nitrates were prepared and standardised⁶. All the aminopolycarboxylic acids were used in their monoprotonated form. The solutions of citraconic (CCA), maleic (MIA), malonic (MLA), phthalic (PHA), oxydiacetic (ODA), malic (MEA) and tartaric (TRA), acids were prepared. A 0.1 M KOH solution was used as the titrant. Initial volume of each solution was 50 ml and the ionic strength kept constant at $\mu=0.1$ M (KNO₃). pH-measurements were carried

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES*

System (1:1:1:1)/(1:1:1)	L	$\log K_{MABL}^M / \log K_{MAB}^M / \log K_{MABL}^{MAB}$				
		La ^{III}	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Gd ^{III}	Dy ^{III}
M(EDTA)(CCA)(L)	MIA	13 50	13 67	13 81	14 15	14 33
	MLA	14 31	14 41	14 55	14 69	14 84
	PHA	14 51	14 75	14 85	14 91	15 08
M(ODTA)(CCA)(L)	MIA	15 48	15 70	15 84	15 89	16 12
	MLA	16 14	16 23	16 38	16 50	16 68
	PHA	16 27	16 53	16 64	16 75	16 92
M(ODA)(MEA)	—	9 35	9 47	9 55	9 65	9 74
M(ODA)(MEA)(L)	IMDA	5 50	5 55	5 60	5 65	5 70
M(ODA)(TRA)	—	8 45	8 59	8 66	8 77	8 86
M(ODA)(TRA)(L)	IMDA	5 33	5 44	5 48	5 53	5 67

*Limit of error $\pm 0.06-0.08$, A=EDTA, ODTA ODA, B=CCA, TRA, MEA

out on a Philips digital pH-meter with a combined assembly of glass (PV 9011) and calomel (PV 9021) electrodes at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. Representative titration curves are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand constants of KIMDA ($pK_1 = 9.05$), K_3 EDTA ($pK_1 = 9.26$), K_3 CDTA ($pK_1 = 11.22$), CCA ($pK_1 = 2.42$, $pK_2 = 5.88$), MIA ($pK_1 = 2.16$, $pK_2 = 6.03$), MLA ($pK_1 = 2.69$, $pK_2 = 5.75$), PHA ($pK_1 = 2.82$, $pK_2 = 5.35$), ODA ($pK_1 = 3.10$, $pK_2 = 4.18$), MEA ($pK_1 = 3.22$, $pK_2 = 4.72$) and TRA ($pK_1 = 2.71$, $pK_2 = 4.09$) were calculated by the method of Cheberek and Martell⁷. Formation constants of ternary and quaternary complexes were evaluated by the modified method⁴ of Ramamoorthy and Santappa⁸ for the simultaneous chelation of the ligands to form quaternary complexes. However, in the case of stepwise addition of the ligands to the metal ion the method of Thompson and Loraas⁹ was applied.

The relative order of the formation constants (Table 1) in terms of metal ions was $La^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Gd^{III} < Dy^{III}$. This could be corrected to the increasing polarisability of the metal ions due to the decreasing size and increasing ionic potential. Stability order for complexes in terms of dicarboxylic acids was $MIA < MLA < PHA$ and for hydroxy acids: $TRA < MEA$ due to the increased basicity of the ligands.

Considering the aminopolycarboxylic acids, the order of stability in terms of these acids has been observed as $EDTA < CDTA$, which may be explained on the basis of increased number of fused ring systems.

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Fungicidal Studies of Manganese(II), Iron(III), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes of Schiff Bases derived from some Sulpha Drugs

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METAL complexes^{1,2} play a vital role in metabolic and toxicological functions in the biological systems. The Schiff bases derived from sulpha drugs and salicylaldehyde have been successfully used as chelating agents³⁻⁶, bactericidal and fungicidal^{7,8} agents. The present paper describes the synthesis, characterisation and fungicidal studies of Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of Schiff bases derived from 5-nitro- and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde with sulphafurazole and sulphamethoxy pyridazine.

Experimental

5-Nitrosalicylaldehyde and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde were synthesised⁹ from salicylaldehyde (S. M.). The sulpha drugs were procured as reported earlier⁴. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade and double-distilled solvents were used throughout. The apparatus and techniques used were as reported earlier⁴.

The Schiff bases were synthesised by refluxing sulpha drug and 5-nitro- and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde in ethanol in 1:1 ratio in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and a few drops of glacial acetic acid for 3-4 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into water and the product was crystallised from acetone.

All the metal complexes were isolated by reacting aqueous solution of metal ion (0.02 M) and acetone solution of Schiff base (0.02 M) in appropriate proportion. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3-4 h and the resulting coloured crystals were washed with water, crystallised from ethanol and dried in an oven ($110-20^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analysis (Table 1) reveal that the Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , and Cu^{II} complexes have 1:2 and the Fe^{II} complexes have 1:3 (M:L) stoichiometry.

The Schiff bases show broad ir bands at ~ 3420 cm^{-1} which is due to the intramolecular hydrogen bonding involving hydrogen of the phenolic group and nitrogen atom of imine group^{10,11}. This band is absent in the spectra of the complexes indicating the replacement of phenolic hydrogen by metal ion and formation of M-O bond. Another notable